

Steric Enhancement of Resonance

M. KRISHNA PILLAY* and SEENI MUBARAK

Department of Chemistry, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli-620 024

Manuscript received 30 October 1991, revised 23 March 1992, accepted 21 May 1992

The concept of steric enhancement of resonance (SER) was proposed by Baliah *et al.*¹ which subsequently got full support². The kinetic data on solvolysis of some *p*-methoxybenzyl bromides gave also convincing evidence for this³. These studies readily led to the conclusion that steric enhancement of resonance can be well recognised in 2-substituted-anisoles with a powerful electron-withdrawing group in 4-position.

In the present paper some ¹³C nmr and ir spectral data are analysed in favour of SER. The ir spectral data of mono-, di- and tri-substituted-anisoles are listed in Table 1. The analysis of the C_{Ar}—O asymmetric stretching frequency furnishes support for this principle. The fact that C_{Ar}—O stretching frequency of compound 5 is lower (1 260 cm⁻¹) than that of 4-nitroanisole (1 263 cm⁻¹) and 2-nitroanisole (1 278 cm⁻¹), indicates the operation of steric inhibition of resonance (SIR).

To confirm SER further, we prepared some suitably substituted phenacyl ethers for recording their ir spectra. The C_{Ar}—O stretching frequencies of phenacyl phenyl ether (1 226 cm⁻¹) are considerably lower than those of phenacyl 2,4-dinitrophenyl ether and phenacyl 4-nitrophenyl ether, which supports SER. Steric inhibition of resonance has been observed in the case of 2,4,6-trinitrophenyl phenacyl ether when the C_{Ar}—O stretching frequency appeared at 1 231 cm⁻¹.

The utility of ¹³C nmr study in detecting SER has been demonstrated by Baliah *et al.*⁴. This prompted us to analyse the ¹³C nmr data of a few substituted anisoles. The chemical shift values of the ring carbons of aromatic ring were calculated using equation (1)⁵,

$$C_s = 128.5 \sum Z_i \quad (1)$$

where Z_i is the additivity of the substituent at carbon i on the chemical shift on C_n carbon. The effects of all substituents including the ipso-substituent have been taken into account. The additivity values for each substituent on different carbon atoms of the benzene ring were taken from the literature⁶. The values obtained by the above computation method have been compared with the literature values of some suitably substituted 4-nitroanisoles and 4-methoxyacetophenones (Table 2). The difference ($\Delta\delta$) between the calculated values and observed values (which were obtained from the computer printout of the NMR machine) has also been presented in Table 2. An analysis-

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE ANISOLES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	ν_{as} C _{Ar} —O cm ⁻¹
1.	Anisole	1 245
2.	2-Nitroanisole	1 278
3.	4-Nitroanisole	1 263
4.	2,4-Dinitroanisole	1 280
5.	2, 4, 6-Trinitroanisole	1 260
6.	PhCOCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₅ **	1 226
7.	PhCOCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄ -NO-4	1 258
8.	PhCOCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₃ -(NO ₂) ₂ -2,4	1 283
9.	PhCOCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₂ -(NO ₂) ₃ -2,4,6	1 231

*Sl. nos. 1 and 2 as liquid film and sl. nos. 3—9 in KBr.

TABLE 2—PREDICTED AND OBSERVED CHEMICAL SHIFTS FOR SUBSTITUTED-ANISOLES

Sl. no.	Substituent	Shielding σ (relative to TMS)						$\Delta\delta$	
		C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₄	C ₆
1.	Unsubstituted	159.9 (159.9)	114.2 (114.1)	129.7 (129.5)	120.9 (120.8)	129.7 (129.5)	114.2 (114.1)	+0.1	+0.1
2.	4-NO ₂	164.9 (165.7)	114.3 (115.0)	126.1 (124.7)	141.8 (140.8)	126.1 (124.7)	114.3 (115.0)	+1.0	-0.7
3.	3-Me, 4-NO ₂	163.2 (166.4)	128.8 (123.9)	126.1 (125.4)	141.3 (140.7)	123.9 (121.8)	109.7 (114.9)	+0.6	-5.2
4.	3-Me, 6-NO ₂ , 6-Me	162.77 (167.1)	132.5 (123.8)	124.4 (122.5)	145.6 (140.6)	124.4 (122.5)	132.5 (123.8)	+5.0	+8.7
5.	4-CO-CH ₃	164.0 (164.1)	114.2 (114.2)	130.8 (129.6)	131.3 (129.9)	130.8 (129.6)	114.2 (114.1)	+1.4	+0.1
6.	2-Me, 4-COCH ₃	161.9 (164.8)	126.7 (123.0)	130.8 (130.3)	130.1 (129.8)	128.7 (126.7)	109.4 (114.0)	+0.3	-4.6
7.	2-Me, 4-COCH ₃ , 6-Me	161.5 (165.3)	131.3 (122.9)	129.7 (127.4)	133.2 (129.7)	129.7 (127.4)	131.3 (122.9)	+3.5	+8.4
8.	2-F, 4-COCH ₃	157.9 (151.2)	146.9 (148.9)	116.5 (116.7)	131.1 (131.3)	126.0 (125.1)	116.5 (115.5)	-0.2	+1.0
9.	2-Cl, 4-COCH ₃	158.7 (164.5)	127.6 (120.3)	130.7 (130.0)	132.1 (131.2)	128.7 (127.7)	111.4 (115.4)	+0.9	-4.0
10.	2-Cl, 4COCH ₃ , 6-Cl	— (164.9)	— (121.6)	129.9 (128.1)	134.0 (132.5)	129.9 (128.1)	— (121.6)	+1.5	—
11.	2-Br, 4-COCH ₃	160.2 (167.5)	112.7 (108.6)	134.2 (133.0)	132.3 (131.6)	129.6 (128.0)	111.6 (115.8)	+0.7	-4.2
12.	2-Br, 4-COCH ₃ , 6-Br	158.6 (170.9)	110.6 (110.3)	135.9 (131.4)	155.5 (133.3)	132.9 (131.4)	110.6 (110.3)	+1.8	+0.3
13.	2-I, 4-COCH ₃	161.8 (174.3)	86.2 (82.1)	140.2 (139.8)	132.0 (132.8)	130.8 (130.6)	110.3 (117.0)	-0.8	-6.7
14.	2-I, 4-COCH ₃ , 6-I	161.8 (184.5)	89.9 (85.01)	139.3 (140.8)	135.9 (135.7)	139.3 (140.8)	89.9 (85.0)	-0.3	+4.9
15.	2-NO ₂ , 4-COCH ₃	156.1 (159.3)	139.3 (134.1)	125.8 (124.8)	129.6 (124.8)	134.2 (135.4)	113.5 (115.0)	-1.2	-1.5
16.	Acetophenone	137.3 (137.6)	128.7 (128.6)	128.5 (128.5)	133.3 (133.3)	128.5 (128.5)	128.7 (128.6)	+0.6	+0.1

^aCalculated values are given in parenthesis.

of $\Delta\delta$ values for the C-4 indicates that δ decreases when we go from 4-substituted-anisoles to 2-substituted-4-nitro/4-acetylanisole and $\Delta\delta$ increases in 2,6-substituted-4-nitro/4-acetylanisoles. The same trend has been observed in similarly substituted acetylanisoles. This confirms that methoxyl group does not feel the steric inhibition of resonance in 2-substituted compound but does feel steric inhibition of resonance in 2,6-disubstituted derivatives.

Another generality results from of ¹³C chemical shift values of anisole pertaining to C-6 atom. In this case, when the 2-substituent is present in 4-nitro/4-acetylanisole an upward shift is observed on the signal of C-6 atom. This is most likely due to the methoxyl group which takes an anti-coplanar conformation (A) and is compatible with the principle of SER.

(A)

R=CH₃, F, Cl, Br, I or NO₂
X=NO₂ or COCH₃

Experimental

All the compounds were prepared by the available procedure². The purity of the compounds was tested by tlc and by gc in the case of liquids. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a JEOL 90Q spectrometer.

References

1. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1960, 25, 21.
2. M. K. PILLAY and S. PALANIVELU, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1987 64, 610 and the references cited therein.
3. V. BALIAH and V. M. KANAGASABAPATHY, *Tetrahedron*, 1978, 38, 3611.
4. V. BALIAH, V. PREMSAGAR, R. K. KUMAR and R. JEYARAMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 151.
5. G. L. LEVY, R. L. LICHTER and G. L. NELSON, "Carbon-13 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1980.
6. F. P. A. LEHMANN and B. D. M. MCEACHERN, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1971, 7, 253.